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“SYMPHONIES OF THE VOICELESS SOULS: A TRADITIONAL HAIKU”

Unconditional

I came to you, then.
And felt your love so deeply
Unconditionally

Joyful Tail

When I first met you
Furry little and tiny
Wagging the joyful tail

Safe Space

She came to this world
Just so innocent and pure
Finding that safe space

My Fur Dad

That man I only knew
Has heart that connects with mom's
Love him so dearly

My Fur Mom

Such a silent soul
Yet always feels when we're sad
Mom never leaves us ill.